

THE IMPACT OF ALGAE EXTRACT APPLICATIONS ON THE YIELD COMPONENTS OF CHICKPEA (*Cicer arietinum*) UNDER DIFFERENT SOIL TEXTURES

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ABSTRACT. This study applied different concentrations of seaweed extract (0, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 1.5, and 2%) to soils with varying textures (clay loam and sandy soils). Chickpea seeds were sown after surface sterilizing the growing medium with a 0.5% sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) solution. The plants were subsequently harvested, and several parameters were measured, including the length of the above-ground plant and root, and the wet and dry weights of both the above-ground parts and roots. The results indicated that applying different doses of seaweed extract had a statistically significant impact on the growth parameters of Azkan chickpea plants in soils with different textures ($p < 0.01$). Higher values were observed in chickpea plants grown in clay loam soil than in those cultivated in sandy soil. In clay loam soil, the 0.75% dose of seaweed extract positively affected the length of the above-ground stem and root. Additionally, the 0.5% dose effectively enhanced the wet and dry weights of both the above-ground parts and roots. The study concluded that a 0.5% dose of seaweed extract significantly improved the fresh and dry weights of the roots. On the other hand, the 0.75% dose had a more substantial effect on the plant height, root length, and the fresh and dry weights of the above-ground parts. In sandy soil, the 0.75% application was found to be more effective in improving all measured parameters.

Keywords: *Chickpea, Growth parameters, Seaweed extract, Soil, Texture*

INTRODUCTION

Seaweed is increasingly utilized as a liquid fertilizer or directly incorporated into the soil in many countries. The direct application to the soil is primarily aimed at enhancing soil structure, which helps maintain long-term soil fertility. Studies have demonstrated that while seaweed extract can be applied both foliarly and to the soil, greater quantities of the extract are typically required for soil applications than foliar treatments [1]. In agriculture, algae serve as both fertilizers and soil regulators. As soil regulators, algae improve the soil's ability to retain water and air, enhance soil structure, and foster a more favorable environment for root growth. Algae are a rich source of biologically active compounds, including alginic acid, vitamins, auxins, at least two types of gibberellins, and antibiotics. Among these, alginic acid plays a critical role in soil regulation, while the other compounds are well-known for their effects on plant growth and development [2,3]. Seaweeds are rich in macro-elements such as phosphorus and potassium, as well as micro-elements like iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), and manganese (Mn), making them valuable fertilizers. Beyond their nutritional content, seaweed extracts serve as plant stimulants. When applied as foliar sprays, they enhance plant growth under stressful conditions like freezing, drought, and salinity, and also improve resistance to fungi, bacteria, and viruses, thereby increasing crop yield and productivity [4-7]. Algal growth is influenced by soil's physical and chemical properties, and upon decomposition, algae enrich the soil by increasing organic matter and releasing essential nutrients. Although algae extracts function

more as biostimulants than conventional fertilizers, they have been shown to promote plant growth and stimulate defense mechanisms when applied [8].

A study identified that the active components of seaweed fertilizers include essential nutrients, amino acids, vitamins, sugars, and growth hormones like auxin, gibberellin, and abscisic acid [9]. Additionally, algal fertilizers enhance soil structure and water retention capacity [10]. In this context, dry algal biomass was tested as a fertilizer in two different soil samples, with results showing that it significantly improved plant growth efficiency when used in place of conventional fertilizers in horticultural systems [11]. Moreover, seaweed and its extracts have been shown to positively influence plant growth, with greater benefits under optimal environmental conditions, including favorable temperature, sufficient water and nutrients, and the absence of harmful pathogens [12]. Soil texture is a crucial physical property that significantly impacts various soil characteristics, including aeration, water holding capacity, nutrient availability, erosion resistance, and workability [13-16].

Furthermore, the physical properties of soil are known to influence the development of plant roots [17,18]. In soils with a high sand content, fertility is often restricted by factors such as low water retention, high infiltration rates, increased evaporation, and low concentrations of organic matter and nutrients. However, when the soil texture transitions from sandy to silt, clay, or silty clay, the number of macropores decreases, water retention improves, and the availability of essential nutrients for plant growth is enhanced [19,20]. The negative impact of sandy soils' properties on soil fertility can be mitigated by incorporating organic matter sources, such as manure, compost, biochar, and vermicompost. Numerous studies have demonstrated that adding organic matter improves the physical, chemical, and biological properties of soil [21,22]. In contrast, the high aggregation rate in clay-textured soils leads to greater physical resistance of organic matter to decomposition. Additionally, clay soils typically contain higher concentrations of organic matter compared to sandy soils [23]. Soil texture plays a crucial role in influencing various soil properties, including its physical and chemical characteristics [24], nutrient content [25], as well as microbial populations and enzyme activity [26,27]. Clay soils, in particular, exhibit a high capacity for the sorption of salt-ionic substances, making them particularly effective in retaining these compounds [28].

This study investigates the effect of sustainable seaweed-based treatments on chickpea growth to reduce dependence on chemical fertilizers. It examines the effects of seaweed extracts applied to soils of different textures to improve plant growth and promote soil health. Using environmentally friendly seaweed, the research addresses environmental and economic concerns associated with chemical fertilizers while improving agricultural sustainability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The soil sample with clay loam texture was collected from the campus of Selçuk University, while the sand-textured soil sample was sourced from Nevşehir province. According to the data presented in Table 1, the properties of the soils with different textures used in the study are as follows: The clay loam soil has a pH value of 7.51, which classifies it as slightly alkaline [29]. Its salinity value indicates that the soil is non-saline [29]. The organic matter content of the clay loam soil is 1.22%, suggesting that it is relatively poor in organic matter. Additionally, the lime content of this soil is 37.3%, placing it in the excess lime category [30]. On the other hand, the sandy soil sample has a pH of 5.5, making it slightly acidic [29]. Its organic matter content is notably low at 0.7%, further indicating a deficiency in organic matter [30]. Furthermore, the lime content of the sandy soil is 0.3%, categorizing it as poor in lime content.

The seaweed utilized in this study is a commercial solid fertilizer product named Proton, which was purchased from the fertilizer company DRT. Proton is derived from the advanced processing of *Ascophyllum nodosum*, a species of seaweed commonly used in agriculture due

to its high biological activity and rich nutrient profile. The chemical properties of the seaweed fertilizer used in this research are detailed in Table 2. As indicated in Table 2, the seaweed extract employed in the experimental study is distinguished by a notably high organic matter content, an alkaline pH, and particularly elevated salinity levels. Additionally, the fertilizer contains 1.5% alginic acid, a key component contributing to its effectiveness as a growth stimulant and soil conditioner. In this study, two distinct soil types, clay loam and sand, were each placed in pots containing 3 kg of soil.

Various doses of seaweed extract (0, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 1.5, and 2%) were applied to these soils to evaluate their effects on the growth of chickpea plants. The Azkan chickpea variety was selected as the test plant for this experiment. Based on the results from soil analysis, the necessary basic fertilization for optimal chickpea growth was applied to both soil types.

Table 1. Some physical and chemical analysis results of soil samples

Parameters	Soil No. 1	Soil No. 2	Method
Texture class	Clay loam	Sandy soil	Bouyoucos, [41]
pH (1:2.5 soil:water)	7.51	5.5	Richards, [42]
EC (1:5 s:w, $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	172	--	U.S. Salinity Lab. Staff, [43]
Lime (%)	37.3	0.3	Hızalan and Ünal, [44]
Organic matter (%)	1.22	0.7	Smith and Weldon, [45]
N ($\text{NH}_4\text{-N} + \text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) (mg kg^{-1})	12.0	24.4	Bremner, [46]
P (available; mg kg^{-1})	10.0	34	Olsen et al. [47]
Extractable mg kg^{-1}	K	162	FAO, [48]
	Ca	5.84	
	Mg	242	
	Na	80	
Favorable mg kg^{-1}	Fe	3.12	Lindsay and Norvell, [49]
	Zn	0.68	
	Mn	5.82	
	Cu	0.67	
mg kg^{-1}	B	0.80	Richards, [42]

Table 2. Some chemical properties of seaweed extract used in the experiment

Parametre	% w/w	MacroE.	% w/w	Micro E.	mg kg^{-1}
Organic matter	43	N	1.9	Fe	200
pH	9-10	P	2.8	Cu	5.8
EC (dSm^{-1})	43.5	K	9.5	Mn	11.8
Protein	6-8	Ca	0.2	Zn	98
Carbohydrates	38-49	S	1.3	B	98
Alginic acid	1.5	Mg	0.6	Mo	3.8
Mannitol	3.5-6.5	Na	1.6		

The experiment was conducted in a greenhouse under controlled conditions, with four replications to ensure accuracy and reliability of the results. The plants were monitored over 45-50 days, and several growth parameters were measured, including stem length, root length, stem fresh and dry weight, and root fresh and dry weight. The data obtained from the greenhouse experiment, which was conducted with four replicates according to the experimental design of the randomized plots, were analyzed using the 'doebioresearch' statistical package in RStudio version 4.1.3 [31]. To identify the most effective treatments, the data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA), and significant differences among treatments were determined using LSD ($p \leq 0.05$) comparisons. This approach facilitated a comprehensive assessment of how varying doses of seaweed extract affected the growth and development of chickpea plants across different soil types.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The application of increasing doses of seaweed extract significantly affected the growth parameters of chickpea plants (**Table 3**). As the doses of seaweed extract increased, plant growth was enhanced, with observable differences in growth depending on the concentration. Additionally, plant yield components improved with higher doses. However, at the highest concentration, the growth of plants began to decline due to the elevated salt content in the seaweed. Specifically, chickpea seeds showed initial germination when a 2% treatment dose was applied to the substrate. However, after 10-15 days post-emergence, plant growth slowed, and the plants ultimately died. The results also indicated statistically significant differences in the length of the plant's upper parts across the treatments ($p < 0.001$).

Fig. 1. The effect of increasing doses of seaweed application on the length of the upper part of chickpea plant in clay loam and sandy soil

The maximum recorded length of the upper part of the chickpea plants was 37.89 cm in the clay loam soil treated with a 0.75% seaweed extract. Conversely, the minimum length of 32 cm was recorded in plants treated with a 1.5% seaweed application (Fig. 1). As the seaweed dose increased, the upper part length of the chickpea plants also increased up to the 1% dose. However, beyond this point, at 1% and 1.5% doses, a decrease in plant growth was observed. Compared to the control plants, seaweed application resulted in a 3.8% increase in the upper

part length. This finding is consistent with Merwad [32], who applied *Ascophyllum nodosum* extract to wheat under salinity stress and found improvements in straw yield, grain yield, plant height, and protein content compared to the control. The differences in root lengths of chickpea plants were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) with increasing doses of seaweed application in both clay loam and sandy soils. The longest root length, measuring 25.89 cm, was observed in plants grown in clay loam soil treated with a 0.75% seaweed extract. In contrast, the shortest root length was recorded in plants treated with a 1.5% seaweed dose (Fig. 2).

It was observed that the root lengths of chickpea plants increased with the application of seaweed extract up to a specific dose. However, root length was decreased at the 1% and 1.5% application doses. When compared to the control plants, seaweed application resulted in a 23% increase in the maximum root length. Similarly, González-González et al. [33] reported that seaweed extract enhanced both root length and weight in tomato plants, along with increased protein content.

Fig. 2. Effect of increasing doses of seaweed application on root length of chickpea plant in clay loam and sandy soil

The differences in the wet weight of the top parts of chickpea plants between treatments were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The highest upper wet weight of 24.1 g was recorded in plants grown on clay loam soil with a 0.5% seaweed treatment, while the lowest weight was observed in plants treated with 1.5% seaweed (Fig. 3). As seaweed application doses increased, the fresh weight of the plant tops also increased, with higher values observed in plants grown on clay loam soils compared to those grown on sandy soils. Compared to the control, seaweed treatment enhanced the maximum top wet weight by 54%. In a similar study, Steveni et al. [34] reported that the application of Maxicrop, a natural seaweed extract, to winter barley led to a 56-63% increase in root, stem, and leaf weights. The highest root wet weight of 24.03 g was recorded in plants grown on sandy soils with a 0.75% seaweed treatment, while the lowest root weight was found in plants grown on clay loam soils with a 1.5% seaweed dose (Fig. 4). Whapham et al. [35] found that weekly application of seaweed extract to cucumber plants in a greenhouse environment had a positive effect on root growth and resulted in a 50% increase in the total dry weight of the plants.

In this study, the results indicated that increasing doses of seaweed extract led to an increase in the dry weight of the plant's upper part (**Fig. 5**). Specifically, dry weights of the upper part increased with up to a 0.5% seaweed application, but decreased with higher doses (0.75%, 1%, and 1.5%). The dry weights of the plant tops ranged from 0.85 to 4.82 g. Furthermore, plants grown in clay loam soils exhibited higher dry weight values compared to those grown in sandy soils.

Fig. 3. The effect of increasing doses of seaweed application on the wet weight of the upper part of chickpea plant in clay loam and sandy soil

Fig. 4. Effect of increasing doses of seaweed application on root wet weight of chickpea plant in clay loam and sandy soil

In conjunction with other organisms, soil algae improve soil properties such as texture, organic matter, and aeration [36]. Foliar or soil treatment of wheat with algal extracts has been shown to promote plant height and dry weight [37], illustrating the positive impact of seaweed extracts on plant growth and development. In the current research, root dry weights of chickpea plants ranged from 0.5 to 2.7 g (Fig. 6). Surprisingly, plants in clay loam soils had higher root

dry weights than plants in sandy soils. Only at the 0.5% seaweed application compared to the control was an increase in root dry weight noted, while higher doses of application reduced the root dry weight. Seaweed extracts have also been reported to positively influence the growth of tomato, zucchini, and marigold plants [38,39]. Additionally, a study conducted by Mattnera et al. [40] revealed that the use of a specific dose of seaweed extract enhanced the development and early growth of broccoli seedlings. Seaweed extract addition was also revealed to significantly boost the overall growth of broccoli plants, further confirming its beneficial effect on plant growth.

Fig. 5. The effect of increasing doses of seaweed application on the dry weight of the upper part of the chickpea plant in clay loam and sandy soil

Fig. 6. The effect of increasing doses of seaweed application on the root dry weight of the chickpea plant in clay loam and sandy soil

Table 3. Effect of increasing doses of seaweed application on some yield components of the chickpea plant in clay loam and sandy soil

Texture	Seaweed Extract Dose (%)	Plant Upper Parts Length (cm)	Root Length (cm)	Fresh Weight of Plant Upper Parts (g)	Root Wet Weight (g)	Plant Upper Part Dry Weight (g)	Root Dry Weight (g)
Clay Loam	0.0	36.52 ab	21.00 d	15.68 d	19.43 c	4.29 b	1.80 c
	0.50	37.00 ab	25.00 a	24.07 a	21.21 b	4.82 a	2.65 a
	0.75	37.89 a	25.89 a	23.01 b	20.30 bc	4.49 b	2.22 b
	1.0	32.35 cd	23.33 b	17.93 c	12.53 e	3.65 c	1.05 e
	1.50	32.00 d	22.22 bc	14.78 e	7.33 f	3.35 d	0.62 f
	2.0	0.00 f	0.00 f	0.00 g	0.00 g	0.00 g	0.00 g
Mean		29.29 A	19.57 A	15.91 A	13.47 A	3.34 A	1.39 A
Sandy soil	0.0	15.00 e	19.00 e	5.98 f	6.43 f	0.85 f	0.50 f
	0.50	36.10 b	21.81 cd	15.21 de	19.87 c	3.29 d	1.37 d
	0.75	37.00 ab	22.44 bc	15.53 de	24.03 a	3.40 cd	2.66 a
	1.0	33.48 c	21.67 cd	14.84 de	17.20 d	2.85 e	1.24 de
	1.50	0.00 f	0.00 f	0.00 g	0.00 g	0.00 g	0.00 g
	2.0	0.00 f	0.00 f	0.00 g	0.00 g	0.00 g	0.00 g
Mean		20.27 B	14.15 B	8.60 B	11.26 B	1.73 B	0.96 B
General Mean		24.78***	16.86***	12.25***	12.36***	2.58***	1.18***
LSD_(0.05)		1.38	1.18	0.85	1.30	0.29	0.21
CV		3.90	4.90	4.82	7.08	7.78	12.23

***; ($P < 0.001$), LSD (Least significant differences) CV: Coefficient of variation

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of seaweed dosages augmented in soils of various textures (clay loam and sandy soils) on the various growth traits of chickpea plants grown under controlled conditions in the greenhouse. In most cases, positive effects of the application of seaweed on plant growth were demonstrated, as well as the potential of seaweed as a substitute for chemical fertilizers as part of green culture. Use of seaweed extracts is a hopeful method for alleviation of the dependency of crops on chemicals in relation to green cultivation. However, the study also revealed the necessity of regulating application rates strictly. It was observed that with an increase in seaweed dose, there was a corresponding increase in the soil salinity, which restricted the growth of plants. Specifically, higher doses resulted in the inhibition of various factors of growth, like shoot and root growth, and with the highest application rates, plant mortality occurred. These findings bring into sharp focus the need to exercise caution when applying seaweed extracts because high concentrations can pose risks to plant health. Therefore, future research should seek to maximize application rates so as to maximize gains from seaweed while minimizing potential adverse effects.

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